

IMPORTANCE OF PREANAESTHETIC STABILIZATION OF A CASE OF POLYTRAUMA FOR OPEN REDUCTION AND INTERNAL FIXATION OF LONG BONE HUMERUS

ABSTRACT

Polytrauma, a patient's condition with multiple injuries that involve multiple organs or systems, is the leading cause of mortality in young adults.

Anaesthesia for trauma patients can be challenging but a multidisciplinary approach with proper planning and communication among the trauma team can help to improve the outcome.

A 36 years old male patient came to hospital with history of fall from height on a construction site with polytrauma and injury at right upper limb, lower limb, pelvic region, abdominal pain, right thoracic pain with multiple rib fractures with associated right side pleural effusion with suspected splenic laceration posted for surgical intervention under general anaesthesia.

Before that patient was admitted in surgical intensive care unit for 10 days preoperatively for stabilization and conservative management with propped up position and incentive spirometry.

After stabilization, patient was taken in operative room, In intraoperative period airway was secured with Endotracheal tube no 8 after induction with Propofol and Rocuronium as a intermediate acting muscle relaxant.

Patient was managed on pressure control mode of ventilator under general anaesthesia so as to avoid barotrauma and usual complications of peripheral nerve blocks after preoperative stabilization of patient in surgical intensive care unit with multimodal approach.

KEYWORD

Preanaesthetic stabilization, polytrauma, long bone fracture, ABG, LAST,

INTRODUCTION

Polytrauma, a patient's condition with multiple injuries that involve multiple organs or systems, is the leading cause of mortality in young adults. Trauma-related injuries are a major public health concern due to their associated morbidity, high disability, associated death, and socioeconomic consequences.[1]

The journey of a polytrauma patient through the stages of pre-hospital care, emergency resuscitation, in-hospital stabilization and rehabilitation pathway can be associated with risks at any of these phases.[1]

In polytrauma cases, long bone fracture and chest trauma can cause severe complications in perioperative period.

There are high chances of complications like fat embolism in case of long bone fractures. And on the other hand chest trauma can affect the normal respiratory mechanism of the human body and can affect the normal homeostasis of human being. Hence, Anaesthesia for trauma patients can be challenging but a multidisciplinary approach with proper planning and communication among the trauma team can help to improve the outcome. The extent of the injury, resuscitation status, co-morbidities need to be considered while planning for perioperative management. The role of

anesthesiologists is crucial in the management of trauma patients and begins in the emergency room resuscitation and continues in the perioperative period and beyond as in chronic pain management. [2]

In case of long bone humerus fracture, various modes of anesthesia like peripheral nerve block (PNB), regional blocks, thoracic or cervical epidural or general anesthesia are available.

There is no consensus in the literature about the safety of Peripheral Nerve Block use in the setting of acute long bone fractures and no conclusions from the literature, as the level of evidence is limited to case reports. Peripheral Nerve Block should be administered to orthopedic trauma patients only in strictly controlled research environments, and surgeons should be highly cautious about using Peripheral Nerve Block for orthopedic long bone fractures, particularly in cases at increased risk for developing acute compartment syndrome (ACS) and Local anesthetic systemic toxicity (LAST). [3]

Also the airway is not patent in case of lateral or wheel chair positioning with Peripheral Nerve Block in case of humerus fracture and there is high chances of respiratory compromise and hence we have decided the mode of anesthesia in this case as general anesthesia.

CASE PRESENTATION

A 36 years old male patient came to hospital with history of fall from height on a construction site with chief complaints of pain at right upper limb, lower limb, pelvic region, abdominal pain, right thoracic pain with multiple rib fractures with associated right side pleural effusion with suspected splenic laceration.

Patient was admitted in surgical intensive care unit for 10 days preoperatively for stabilization and conservative management.

On day one, patient came with decreased hemoglobin 7 mg/dl with right sided polytrauma with suspected internal and external bleeding.

Patient maintained SpO₂- 80-90% in initial 6-7 days with oxygen support only.

Arterial Blood Gas analysis shows borderline metabolic acidosis with PH- 7.3 and pO₂ - 78 mmHg. Bleeding parameters PT/INR - 17.20/ 1.42.

Patient was further investigated with X-ray chest, Ultrasonography chest and abdomen & pelvis.

Surgical and radiological opinion was to tap the pleural effusion but because of the difficulty in positioning the tapping was not possible.

Intra & Extra abdominal bleeding was ruled out.

The hemodynamics was managed with blood transfusion and Injection Vitamin K 30 mg stat and 10 mg twice for 3 days.

Incentive spirometry was started for respiratory exercises and propped up position was advised to the patient throughout the hospital stay.

After 10 days surgical intensive care unit stay, patient was able to maintain SpO₂ > 90% on room air and above 94% on oxygen support with propped up position.

Patients recent arterial blood gas (ABG) analysed and was normal and hence patient posted for surgical intervention under general anaesthesia.

Why general anesthesia as a mode of anesthesia irrespective of other mode?

- Safe anaesthesia saves life.
- Securing airway in surgeries of Head, Neck and Face (HNF) and near HNF makes it difficult to secure airway intraoperatively.

- Interscalene block for humerus involves risk of Horner's syndrome, which the affect the functioning of ipsilateral diaphragm, which have added to more respiratory insufficiency.
- Longer duration of surgeries like in this case, peripheral nerve blocks can make patient uncomfortable after 1-1.5 hours.

Hence in this case preferred mode of anesthesia was general anesthesia.

Figure 1: Chest X-ray on day 0

Syringe Diagnostic 348	
Blood Gas Report	
348-6403 23:01 10 Sep 2024	
Sample No. 21844 Syringe	
Operator: ID	
Patient: ID 11993247	
Measured	37 °C
pH	7.404
pCO2	37.3 mmHg
pO2	74.1 ↓ mmHg
Na+	132 ↓ mmol/L
K+	4.81 mmol/L
Cl-	100 mmol/L
Hct	35 %
T, ↓ = outside ref. range	
Reference Ranges	
pO2	80.0 - 100.0
Na+	135 - 148
Calculated Data	
HCO3act	22.6 mmol/L
HCO3std	23.1 mmol/L
BE(ser)	-1.8 mmol/L
BE(B)	-1.8 mmol/L
ctCO2	24.0 mmol/L
Ca++(7.4)	
AnGap	14.1 mmol/L
O2SAT	95.0 %
O2CT	15.9 mL/dL
ctHb(est)	11.8 g/dL
pO2/FiO2	
pO2(A-a)	
pO2(a/A)	

Figure 2: ABG on day 0

Patient was taken in operative room, In intraoperative period airway was secured with Endotracheal tube no 8 (oral intubation) after induction with standard dose of Propofol 200 mg (2-2.5 mg/kg) and Rocuronium 70 mg (0.8-1.2mg/kg) as a intermediate acting muscle relaxant.

Patient was managed on pressure control mode of ventilator under general anaesthesia for 4 to 5 hours till the surgical procedure completed.

The regional anesthesia avoided so as to secure airway and collapsed alveoli was restored with elective intubation.

In preoperative and intraoperative period patient was vitally stable and procedure was uneventful.

In post operative period patient was planned to ventilate for 4-5 hours electively but maintained SpO2 saturation on T piece immediately after 30 min postoperatively and did not tolerate endotracheal tube, so patient extubated successfully within half hour postoperatively.

Figure 3: Chest X-ray on day 7

Blood Gas Report	
348-6403	00:42 5 Sep 2024
Sample No.	21754 Syringe
Operator ID	
Patient ID	1190090
Measured	
37 °C	
pH	7.349 ↓
pCO2	32.3 ↓ mmHg
pO2	78.0 ↓ mmHg
Na+	136 mmol/L
K+	1.73 ↓ mmol/L
Cl-	106 mmol/L
Hct	22 ↓ %
T. ↓ = outside ref. range	
Reference Ranges	
pH	7.350 - 7.450
pCO2	35.0 - 45.0
pO2	80.0 - 100.0
K+	3.50 - 5.10
Hct	34 - 52
Calculated Data	
HCO3act	17.3 mmol/L
HCO3std	18.2 mmol/L
BE(eCF)	-8.3 mmol/L
BE(CB)	-7.5 mmol/L
ctCO2	18.3 mmol/L
Ca++(7.4)	
AnGap	18.5 mmol/L
OSAT	85.1 %
GCCT	10.2 mL/dL
ctHb(CoSt)	7.5 g/dL
pO2/FiO2	
pO2(A-a)	
pO2(a/A)	

Figure 4: ABG on day 7

DISCUSSION

Polytrauma, a patient's condition with multiple injuries that involve multiple organs or systems, is the leading cause of mortality in young adults. Trauma-related injuries are a major public health concern due to their associated morbidity, high disability, associated death, and socioeconomic consequences. [1]

Regional analgesia should be considered early in all highrisk (multiple fractures, flail chest, advanced age, other injuries) rib fracture situations. In-hospital patients need to be reevaluated frequently to ensure adequate analgesia. If the clinical picture deteriorates (e.g., progressive respiratory failure), the need for regional blocks and/or rib plating should be considered. Although there are insufficient data to date to show reductions in mortality with regional blocks, the improved analgesia and reduction of opioid requirements provided by regional blocks are a worthy endpoint in itself. Furthermore, inadequate analgesia and over reliance on opioids for acute pain increase the risk of chronic opioid dependency.[4] hence in this case study we have decided the general anesthesia as a mode of anesthesia and this eliminates complications such as acute compartment syndrome or related nerve injuries and also avoids the neuromuscular monitoring and related complications.

Another mode such as thoracic epidural anesthesia and analgesia (TEA) is also available and it may positively affect cardiopulmonary function in the perioperative period. Moreover, this technique leads to an earlier return of gastrointestinal function and early ambulation without severe postoperative complications, resulting in a shortened hospital stay and lowered costs.[5] but it has more procedural complexities as compared to general anesthesia and it also need neuromuscular monitoring and maintenance by top up doses.

Hence, general anesthesia is relatively more easier and quick to perform and also airway maintain patent by intubation with endotracheal tube. But we need to avoid mechanical damage by preventing excessive ventilation and hence lung protective ventilatory strategy was used.

Nada Ismaiel et.al stated that mechanical damage is best attenuated by limiting tidal volume and transpulmonary driving pressures, to minimize excessive stretch and strain. The combined reduction of these mechanical mechanisms is believed to minimize traumatic cell death and promote apoptosis in the lung. The therapeutic effects of hypercapnia appear to extend beyond the lungs to distant organs, where the spontaneous rise in CO₂ attenuated histologic liver injury with permissive hypercapnia. These findings suggest that combining ventilation strategies that integrate lung-protective settings that limit tidal volumes, minute ventilation and driving pressures with permissive hypercapnia as an accepted side effect may offer the best protection against Ventilator associated lung injury (VALI). Lung-protective ventilation may limit mechanical damage to the lung, while hypercapnia attenuates VALI by limiting pro-inflammatory and biochemical mechanisms of injury. When combined, both have the potential to exert a synergistic effect for prevention of VALI and its systemic effects. [6]

Our results are encouraging and hold clinical implications for the future of research on VALI and clinical practice as the medical community makes the leap from the bench to the bedside.

CONCLUSION

A case of polytrauma for open reduction and internal fixation of long bone humerus was successfully managed on pressure control mode of ventilator under general anaesthesia so as to avoid barotrauma and usual complications of peripheral nerve blocks after preoperative stabilization of patient in surgical intensive care unit with multimodal approach such as incentive spirometry.

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